

Addressing Gender-Based Violence Amidst of the Quest for Digital Economy and Beyond the Warzone in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study address Gender-Based Violence (GBV) amidst the quest for digital economy and beyond the warzone in Northern Nigeria. In the recent years, digital economy has emerged as a transformative force, revolutionizing various sectors locally and as well globally. The realization of digital economy can be hard if GBV thrives in our communities like nowadays. The paper aims to uncover the acts of Gender-based violence as it occurs in north. It happens within the home setting or the wider community, affecting women, men and children disproportionately. In Northern Nigeria, it is an ongoing challenge that can only be understood in its socio-cultural, religious and economic contexts. However, intensive research into Gender-Based Violence in Nigeria within the context of socio-religious conflict remains very low, inconsistent and in some instances totally ignored. This particular research adopts qualitative method as it investigates Gender-Based Violence specifically against Christian women/men and children in the context of homes amidst the quest for digital economy and beyond the warzones. The study finds out that the years 2015 and 2023 are to a large extent, considered as the period to which the emergence of Banditry and kidnapping could be traced. This period then provides acts of GBV and as well the basis to embrace digitalization as a welcome development. In summation, the study gives a highlight on the consequences of Gender-Based Violence and beyond the warzone. Flourishing should be key in our society not the unpleasant result of GBV which could be physical, psychological, social, economic and also spiritual in nature. The study recommends that further research on the contribution of education and digitalization in curbing the acts of GBV should be carried out. This would go a long way address GBV in our contemporary society today.

Keywords: Gender-based violence, Digitalization, Digital Economy, Warzone, Banditry, Kidnapping and Northern Nigeria

Introduction

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is a global health, development, humanitarian, and human rights issue with many consequences especially to those directly affected by it.¹ It is indeed one of the most prevalent human rights violations in the world today that cares not about social, economic or national boundaries but vastly under-reported². In some occasions, GBV is considered not violence but gender disparity. This analysis considers it as violence. It occurs worldwide despite the provision for equal rights and status as stipulated in international legal instruments which have dealt extensively with this issue³ Even though GBV is mostly associated with countries experiencing conflict, the reality is that it is present everywhere in the world. It happened in various forms such as domestic violence, harassment, rape and the marginalization of girls and women/men cutting across cultures and nations.⁴

Addressing Gender Based Violence amidst the Quest for Digital Economy

It is worthy of note that the advent of the digital economy/age (economy driven by digital technologies) has brought about unprecedented advancements in technology, transforming the way individual and organizations interact and operate. The quest for digital economy can only be achieved when GBV is well addressed. Since GBV is a global phenomenon, getting scholars to accept a common classification for the phenomenon has been a very difficult thing. Thus, attempts to define the concept have aroused argument among members of the

intellectual community. As such, this study agrees that there is a quite varied definition of GBV. For example, the Inter-Agency Standing Committee gives the definition of GBV to mean, "... an umbrella term for any harmful act that is perpetrated against a person's will and that is based on socially ascribed (i.e. gender) differences between males and females. It includes acts that inflict physical, sexual or mental harms or suffering, threats of such acts, coercion, and other deprivations of liberty. These acts can occur in public or in private."⁵

This is to say that GBV is any act that is likely to result in physical, sexual, psychological harm or suffering, economic, or spiritual abuse to women/men, including threats of such act, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring at home, workplace, or within a given community.⁶ Similarly, Sida⁷ defines Gender-Based Violence as: "Any harm or suffering that is perpetrated against a woman or girl, man or boy and that has a negative impact on the physical, sexual or psychological health, development or identity of the person. The cause of the violence is founded in gender-based power inequalities and gender-based discrimination." According to Heise,⁸ the term GBV came to be within the women's rights movement in order to articulate women's exposure to violence especially in the context of patriarchy. It is observed that the term was first taken up in the United Nations (UN) Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women⁹, which was an international agreement in which Violence Against Women (VAW) was defined to mean "any act of gender based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women."¹⁰

Furthermore, United Nations, Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women emphasizes that GBV takes many forms by making the link between patriarchy and GBV clear by asserting that violence against women is "a manifestation of historically unequal power relations between men and women, which have led to the domination over, and discrimination against women, by men and to the prevention of the full advancement of women."¹¹ Since United Nations, Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women promulgation of VAW to mean GBV in 1993, record has it that, many definitions of GBV have emanated. Some of these definitions reflect a gradual but a significant shift away from a specific emphasis on gender discrimination as is found in VAWG¹². For example, some conceptualize the term 'gender-based violence' as used by some actors to describe violence perpetrated against Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Intersex (LGBTQI) persons.¹³

This study considers Gender - Based Violence to mean any acts that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women or men. This is to say that in this study GBV refers to violence that is directed against a woman/man because she/he is a woman/man or that affects both women and men disproportionately. The reason of using the above definition is because, in Northern Nigeria the acts of GBV are mostly targeted to women and girls due to patriarchy and power imbalance within families, communities and the society.¹⁴ This is also true that in Africa the common notion that men are superior to women contribute to the factors that cause GBV within the continent and as well in Northern Nigeria¹⁵ Based on the aforementioned explanations, the study agrees that GBV is as violence, targeted to someone because of his or her gender which occurs between men and women in relationships, in the home, at the workplace and in the community. It also occurs among racial, clan, religious, ethnic and political groups. Thus, gender violence is about power and control and mostly perpetrated at warzones by bandits, kidnappers and the Boko Haram militia.¹⁶

Acts of Gender Based-Violence amidst the Quest for Digital Economy in Northern Nigeria

In the recent decade, Northern Nigeria has been bedeviled with lots of insurrections ranging from banditry, kidnapping, Fulani herdsmen, and the Boko Haram sect. The quest for digitalization has been marred due to the volatile nature of the region. As such, the study likened GBV to a bomb blast at a warzone, because it affects those within and causes a colossal damage even to those without. It does not just affect this generation but other generation because it has a multi-generational impact. It takes the form of physical, emotional, sexual, economic or spiritual abuse. Examples are rape, domestic violence, and sexual harassment. It creates fear, breaks down self-esteem, and makes people do things they do not want to do, limits behavior, movement, and it physically harms¹⁷

Like in Northern Nigeria, there exist many factors behind GBV today and has been itemize by various scholars. Jewkes¹⁸ and Heise observes that, GBV originates from patriarchy. The root meaning of patriarchy is based on the Latin word father, pater, which literally means the rule of the father or fathers¹⁹. Again, the word patriarchy is derived from the two Greek words patēr and archē literally meaning the rule of the father in a male dominated family or rule of the pateres (fathers)²⁰. Therefore, patriarchy is a type of “power-over” situation, and the term is used in description of the multiple structures, beliefs and practices which ensure that men exercise power over women²¹. Thus, in a patriarchal and matriarchal system, female and male human beings are considered as inferior in all the aspect of life and inherently of lesser value than male or the female.

In a patriarchal and matriarchal society, the control and domination of male/female and other family members is legitimated and mostly practice in a violent manner²². Therefore, GBV is rooted in structural gender inequalities, patriarchy, matriarchy (matriarchy is a system where women exercise power over men) and power imbalances. This is why Bradley²³ submits that patriarchy is responsible for creating and maintaining a system that leaves women vulnerable to male control, which is often violent and causes GBV. It is evident also according to Van der Westhuizen²⁴ that, patriarchy do not only determine a woman’s position in this society, but it also explains women’s experience of social power. The common assertion is that patriarchy recognizes the power that women can have and the actual power of men. Therefore, one is tempted to say that the purpose of patriarchy is to destroy a woman’s consciousness about her potential power.

In support of the above analogy, Rachel Jewkes describes the causes of GBV in terms of a constellation of some factors.²⁵ The core reasons for the constellation of factors are the culture of violence and patriarchy. Jewkes’s causality theory states that a combination of patriarchal values and traditional or social values that engender violent conflict resolution is very highly likely to result in GBV. Under such circumstances, since male dominance is part of socialization in terms of gender relations, conflicts are traditionally or socially settled through cruelty or sexual violence. Furthermore, the cultural socialization through which some cultures teach boys from their early age to repress feelings of fear and pain and to channel all their emotions into anger is another cause of GBV²⁶. In a situation like this, societies have also established male norms as leaders and authority figures, independent, strong, aggressive, sexually assertive and successful, ambitious, and competitive. In contrast females are cast as followers, obedient, dependent, weak and passive, chaste, gentle, nice and kind.

Like in Northern Nigeria and in Africa as a whole, Iyamkaremye²⁷ opined that GBV thrives where a set of customs, traditions, and taboos which, for example, allow men to beat their wives for different reasons, such as transgression of women’s culturally prescribed role or being disobedient. The common gendered role division through which men are always the final decision-makers and are assigned public, formal and best paid activities while women have to remain obedient and to carry out private, informal, less paid and time-consuming activities is another contributing factor to GBV.²⁸ Heise states that, at the societal level studies around the world have found that Violence Against Women (VAW) is most common than Violence Against Men (VAM). This comes to bare where gender roles are rigidly defined and enforced and where the concept of masculinity is linked to toughness, male honor, or dominance. Other cultural norms associated with abuse include tolerance of physical punishment of women and children, acceptance of violence as a means to settle interpersonal disputes, and the perception that men have “ownership” of women as well as the entire household.²⁹

At the societal level, norms that grants men control over female behavior cause GBV. Also, the acceptance of violence as a way to resolve conflict as well as the notion of masculinity that linked to dominance, honor and aggression with rigid gender roles contribute to the cause of GBV. At the community level, poverty, low sociological status, unemployment causes GBV³⁰. It is observed that women’s isolation and lack of social support, together with male peer groups that condone and legitimize men’s violence, predict higher rates of violence and in essence GBV.³¹ On the relationship level, marital conflict, male control of wealth and decision making as a result of patriarchy in the family cause GBV and well hamper effort for digitalization. On individual perpetrator level, these factors may include being abused as a child or witnessing marital violence in the home, having an absent or rejecting father, and frequent use of alcohol³².

On the other hand, it is observed that the root causes of GBV lies in the society's attitude towards and practices of gender discrimination. For example, abuse of power, gender inequality and lack of belief in equality of human rights for all. The patriarchal interpretation of the Scriptures can also be seen as a contributing factor to GBV. With example of the Hebrew Bible, some texts such as Genesis 2:18-25 have been used to insist that a woman is lower because she was created second.³³

Spiritual connotation of Gender Based Violence

Spiritually, the way in which some scriptures are interpreted out of context during sermons contribute to GBV. Examples of these scriptures include Genesis 34:2; 25-29; Judges 11:34-40; 19-21 and 2 Samuel 11:1-27; 13:11-14; 19-20. These texts portray violence against women such as Schechem and Dinah, Jephtha and his daughter, the Levite and his concubine, David and Bathsheba, Amnon and Tamar respectfully. Another instance is in Genesis 19, like in Judges 19-21 which Lot offered his daughters to the men of Sodom when they wanted to attack the men that visited Lot. He pleaded with the men of Sodom, "Behold, I have two daughters who have not known a man; let me bring them out to you, and do to them as you please; only do nothing to these men, for they have come under the shelter of my roof" (Gen. 19:8). In spite of this action, Lot is still remembered in Christian tradition as a righteous man (cf. 2 Peter 2:7).

In addition, the banishment of Queen Vashti from her royal position because she refused to display her beauty in the public (Esther 1) is another example of GBV. One can say that, even though the Bible may seem to be silent on some of these violent cases against women, it is not a sufficient ground for anybody to use the Bible to support GBV. Similarly, Jewkes³⁴ argues that, drug and alcohol abuse, poverty, conflict, collapse of traditional society and family support system contributes to GBV. Others factors are, lack of police protection, impunity, loss of male power/role in the family and community; seeking to assert power. The use GBV as a weapon of war, lack of education and separation from family members and social breakdown contribute to GBV (WHO, 2000). In essence, patriarchy which is a system of social structure and practices in which men dominate, oppress and exploit women facilitates various cultural, legal, economic and political cause to GBV.³⁵ Concisely, Jewkes³⁶ enumerates the following as factors that contributes to GBV: a) poverty, culture and the ideology of male dominance; b) power, and sexual identity; c) women and power; d) relationship conflict; e) alcohol; and f) social norms

Consequences of Gender Based Violence and Beyond the 'Warzone'

Beyond the 'warzone,' the unpleasant results of GBV either from kidnapping, banditry, Boko Haram terrorist or raping has lots of consequences. These consequences are multifaceted and in manifold as they include, physical, psychological, stigma and discrimination, socio-economical and spiritual consequences. Physically, GBV may result in head injuries, internal bleeding, pain, death and problems of walking and carrying activities³⁷. Fatal outcomes will be, homicide, suicide, and loss of life, maternal mortality and AIDS related sickness. While nonfatal outcomes will be functional impairment and the physical symptoms are, poor subjective health, permanent disability and severe obesity³⁸. Health wise, it causes cardiovascular, neurological, pulmonary, musculoskeletal, gastrointestinal, mental problem and many others³⁹. On the other hand, it also facilitates the high prevalence of HIV and AIDS resulting from the inability to negotiate safer sex, and/or the inability to refuse unwanted sex. In some instances, it also causes unwanted abortion when abuse occurs during pregnancy⁴⁰. Sexually and on reproductive levels, it causes traumatic gynecologic fistula, an injury resulting from severe tearing of the vaginal tissues, rendering the woman to be mentally ill or socially undesirable.⁴¹

Psychologically,⁴² survivors of GBV are often left traumatized. GBV also leads to personality and mood disorders; memory loss; anxiety; psychosis; and posttraumatic stress disorder. Mental distress expressed in crying easily, inability to enjoy life, fatigue, dizziness and thoughts of suicide, substance abuse, and use of medication are also consequences of GBV⁴³. Subsequently, GBV causes stigmatization, emotional, depressive problems through despair, fear, self-blame, grief, loss of sense of self, loss of self-confidence and self-esteem, feelings of

helplessness, anger, and powerlessness.⁴⁴ The repercussions of the aforementioned consequence are severe, making women vulnerable to emotional abuse in marital problems such as mistrust, shame, guilt, fear of sexual activities, revenge and withdrawal from society⁴⁵. Beyond the direct and short-term consequences, child witnesses of violence are more likely to have emotional and behavioral problems, perform poorly in school and be at risk of perpetrating or experiencing violence in the future⁴⁶. Beyond the warzone, stigma and discrimination is another consequence of GBV. Le Roux⁴⁷ asserts that survivors of GBV faces the challenges of stigmatization by their family and community. Stigma which is a situation of an individual who is disqualified from full social acceptance, happens when power is enacted in order to identify, stereotype and label the differentness of socially deviant individual.⁴⁸

On socio-economic aspect, this study agrees with Iyakaremye and Ishola⁴⁹ that socially, GBV makes survivors lose friends, property, and rejection by family and community as well as their human dignity. Again, it makes an abused woman a prisoner in her own house, where she suffers loss of friends, family and self-respect⁵⁰. Furthermore, women are displaced as a result GBV from their homes and lands, while their children are left without mothers to take care of them and young girls are forced into sexual trade⁵¹. Financial consequences of GBV range from the denial of access to resources to pressure to incur debts in the abuser's name. Here, there is a problem with women's prospects of securing their own income from employment for many are forced to leave paid work or have their income confiscated⁵². In a nutshell, GBV is inimical since it contributes to the impoverishment of families and communities.

Once again, beyond the 'warzone' GBV causes a loss of employment, social, or political participation opportunities; and expenditures to women. This happened at the level of individual, family and public sector budgets. This is glaring most especially on medical, protection, judicial and social services⁵³. As a consequence, businesses and employers incur financial losses on account of absences due to the health significances inhibiting the survivor. This could be from working; incarceration of the perpetrator; and expenses related to additional security measures that might be needed in the workplace.⁵⁴

The spiritual consequences of GBV can be seen in the way abused women are forced to believe that their abuse is God's will. This is because in some patriarchal religious teachings are identified in some texts as clearly supporting violence to discipline women.⁵⁵ Iyakaremye⁵⁶ highlights that, "in some Christian families, the letter of Paul to Ephesians is used to compel wives to unquestionably submit to their husbands as to the Lord. Here, only the husband's points of view and practices regarding financial, spiritual, social, and sexual aspects are considered as legitimate and God's inspiration." Hence, women who happen to perceive this patriarchal and anti-woman abuse and dare to question it and are tempted to leave it to their religions and churches. From the above discourse, it is worthy of note that in this study women are the most wounded of GBV even though at times men also suffer from it, but women are the most targeted and as such, both men and women need to condemn it.⁵⁷ Others who suffer GBV include, children, teenagers, vulnerable men, boys, sexual minorities, and those with gender-nonconforming identities, though this is not the goal of this study.⁵⁸

Conclusion

Addressing Gender-Based Violence amidst the quest of digital economy and beyond the warzone in Northern Nigeria is a task that must be done with the sense of urgency. Condemning the acts of GBV should be taken seriously by all well-meaning citizens of any nation for meaningful development such as digital economy and as well peace and justice to thrive. Since GBV is not a blessing to every nation, a collective effort in combating its acts which are common mostly through banditry, kidnapping, and Boko Haram atrocities. This effort in Northern Nigeria is indeed timely. Thus, gender equality is achieved when women and men, girls and boys, have equal rights, life prospects and opportunities, and the power to shape their own lives and contribute to society.

It is indeed noteworthy to remember that GBV is happening everywhere. It acts are in no doubt multifaceted. In most cases, the acts are under-reported worldwide. This is due to fears of stigma or retaliation. Also limited availability or accessibility of trusted service providers, impunity for perpetrators, and lack of

awareness of the benefits of seeking care as pinpointed by Inter-Agency Standing Committee. As such waiting for or seeking a population-based data on the true magnitude of GBV in our communities should not be a priority in an emergency due to safety and ethical challenges in collecting such data may arise. However, the study submits that not all GBV is violence but can rather be classified as disparity. Thus, a quality attention in addressing GBV amidst the quest for digital economy and beyond the warzone in Northern Nigeria is key and in developing nations for citizens to flourish. The study recommends that further research on the contribution of education and digitalization in curbing the acts of GBV should be carried out. This would go a long way address the deeds of GBV in our contemporary society today.

Endnotes

¹E. Le Roux and L. Loots, “The Unhealthy Divide: How the Secular-Faith Binary Potentially Limits GBV Prevention and Response”. *Development in Practice*, vol. 27, no. 5, 2017, 733–744 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2017.1327023> and O. Yusuf, O. B Oladepo, and O. S. Arulogun, “Factors Influencing Gender Based Violence among Men and Women in Selected States in Nigeria. African.” *Journal of Reproductive Health*, 2011, 78-86.

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⁴M. Hynes, J. Ward, C. Robertson, et al., “A Determination of the Prevalence of Gender-Based Violence among Conflict Affected Populations in East Timor.” *Disasters*. 2004, 28(3), 294–321 and E. Fulu, and S. Miedema, “Violence against Women: Globalizing the Integrated Ecological Model,” *Violence against Women* Vol. 21(12) 2015, 1431–1455.

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⁷Sida. 2007. “Action Plan for Sida’s Work against Gender-Based Violence 2008-2010. SidaGenderSecretariat. http://www.sida.se/contentassets/b7c778a855dc4e92a5a9da1bebc48b0a/action-plan-for-sidas-workagainst-gender-based-violence-2008-2010_680.

⁸L. Heise, assert that the Coalition of Feminists for Social Change (COFEM), and was created in 2017 to reassert a feminist perspective in violence against women and girls (VAWG). The work is a collection of over 80 activists, academics, and practitioners working globally to end VAWG. The Feminist Perspectives on Addressing Violence Against Women and Girls Series as well as a collection of papers written by COFEM members to articulate concerns and aspirations for the shrinking space for feminist analysis in VAWG efforts in development and humanitarian settings.

⁹*Ibid.*, 2-4.

¹⁰Heise, L. 1998:2-3.

¹¹United Nations, Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women, United Nations, New York, 20December1993. Available at :< <http://www.un.org/documents/ga/res/48/a48r104.htm>>. Some might argue that because DEVAW articulates VAW as GBV (rather than the reverse), it can be assumed that there may be “other types” of GBV that are not VAW. Such an interpretation may rest on a certain logic or literalness that overlooks how “gender” was understood and used by many women’s rights activists at the time DEVAW was drafted (and up to the present), as a word to describe the socially imposed hierarchy between males and females. When taking this into account, there can be no confusion that GBV specifically delineates the problem of VAWG.

¹²Heise, L. 1998. Talking about Feminists for Social Change.

¹³Inter-Agency Standing Committee. 2015. Guidelines for Integrating Gender-Based Violence Interventions in Humanitarian Action: Reducing risk, promoting resilience and aiding recovery.

¹⁴L. Heise, 1998. the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) states that GBV is rooted in structural gender inequalities, patriarchy, and power imbalances. This is to say that GBV is typically characterized by the use or threat of physical, psychological, sexual, economic, legal, political, social and other forms of control and/or abuse of women and girls across the life course are most at-risk and disproportionately affected.

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